

Reproducing “A Framework for Analyzing the Impact of Missing Data in Predictive Models”

Christoph Eder
Vienna University of Technology
Austria

Julia Oberauer
Vienna University of Technology
Austria

Isabella Stöckler
Vienna University of Technology
Austria

ABSTRACT

The aim of this project was to reproduce the experiments and potentially verify the results from the paper "A Framework for Analyzing the Impact of Missing Data in Predictive Models" [2]. This included the creation of a simulated input data sets with artificially added missing data, collecting the model accuracy of logistic regression models fit to this data and quantifying the impact of each input parameter with the help of another linear regression model. Even though we had to compromise regarding the number of simulation runs and configurations we were able to partially confirm the results of the original work.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Information systems** → Incomplete data.

KEYWORDS

Data Simulation; Missing Data; Predictive Model; Reproducibility

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1 INTRODUCTION

The reproducibility of scientific work is essential in understanding processes. Therefore the aim of this project was to reproduce the paper "A Framework for Analyzing the Impact of Missing Data in Predictive Models" [2]. This allows a deeper understanding on how to cite data and helps to improve the quality of scientific work overall. For the reproduction of the paper R version 4.1.2 with the packages `tidyr` version 1.1.4, `ggplot2` version 3.3.5 and `dplyr` version 1.0.7 was used. All the created data and the developed code is available on Zenodo ¹.

2 OUTLINE OF ORIGINAL PAPER

The paper aims to quantify the impact of missing data points in predictive models. In order to do so, the authors generate a range of data sets with varying parameters from which they then artificially remove data. These parameters include sample size, number of variables and correlation of input variables. To simulate different types of inputs (binary, continuous, categorical) different distributions are used to generate the data. Removing data is done according to different patterns (MCAR, MNAR, MAR). As a next step, the authors fit

multiple logistic regression models with generated response variables for each input setting and compute the accuracy. Afterwards, a linear regression model is fit on accuracy to get the impact of each input parameter and the results are visualized.

3 STRATEGY

As a first step the paper was analyzed after which a strategy was developed to reproduce it.

3.1 Data Generation

To replicate the paper we first need to generate the input data, as it was done in in the original experiment. Fortunately for us, the entire code used for the simulation was provided on a public github repository by the authors of the paper².

3.2 Fitting Models and analysing accuracy

As soon as the data is generated, we should be able to fit logistic regression models for each of the parameter settings included. This subsequently allows us to calculate the accuracy for each of the fitted models and add the information to our data set. As in the previous step, the code for this part of the experiment is provided on github¹.

3.3 Quantifying impact of parameters on accuracy

With the additional information on accuracy that we gain in 3.2, we could then try to quantify the impact of each input parameter on the accuracy. In order to do this, we plan to fit a linear regression model, as suggested by the authors, with accuracy as the response and all the other parameters as explanatory variables and interpret the resulting regression coefficients.

3.4 Comparison and Visualisation

As a final step, we want to compare the regression coefficients to the findings in the paper. When doing this, we especially try to focus on the sign and magnitude of the coefficients rather than the exact values. We also plan on recreating the plot in the original paper if possible.

4 REPRODUCING THE PAPER

Following the strategy described above, we made an attempt to reproduce the findings of the paper.

4.1 Data Generation

In this step, we generate the covariates for the logistic regression models in the simulation as well as some additional information

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5913142>

²https://github.com/fsantore/missing_data_analysis

for each observation, which we need for further analysis of the results. As mentioned earlier, the code was provided on Github. Our first attempt of running it did not work as planned, since we severely underestimated the computation time of the project. After an unsuccessful attempt to let it run locally overnight, we followed the suggestion to try to run it on Google Colab. There, we encountered the problem, that without a pro licence, the execution randomly stops, if computational power is needed by a pro user [1]. In our case this always happened after 3 to 4 hours. As a last resort, we went back to running it locally, but for a longer period of time. After roughly 32 hours, the execution finished and we could finally examine the results. Alternatively, if this had not worked, we would have reduced the number of observations generated. The effect size is calculated with the NORTA ("Normal to anything") algorithm.

Table 1: First 6 output rows as an example

ind	acc	n	j	pref	dist	rho	eff
"1"	0.9	500	10	0.2	"binomial"	0	12.96
"1"	0.9	500	10	0.2	"binomial"	0.5	5.78
"1"	0.9	500	10	0.2	"poisson"	0	13.4
"1"	0.9	500	10	0.2	"poisson"	0.8	5.37
"1"	0.9	500	10	0.5	"normal"	0.5	6.08
"1"	0.9	500	10	0.2	"normal"	0	13.48

The output shown in table 1 contains the following parameters:

- ind**: index generated by write.table
- acc**: accuracy, fixed at 0.9
- n**: sample size
- j**: number of input variables
- pref**: predictive power of input variables
- dist**: distribution from which generated data is derived
- rho**: correlation between input variables
- eff**: effect size

Further explanations

The `ind` is only part of our output, because it is included in the authors' setup and we did not want to modify any of it. The `acc` is fixed at 0.9 for this step, since it only serves as a parameter used for deriving the effect size. `n`, in this case is a factor with three levels: 500, 1000 and 10000 observations. The number of input variables `j` is a factor with the levels 10, 100 and 200. The predictive power of input variables is a score between 0 and 1 that quantifies how "useful" an input variable is for the prediction of the response. The closer to 1 the score is, the higher the predictive power of the variable. In our case, it is represented as a factor with the levels 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8. The `dist` variable refers to the distribution from which the sample is drawn. It has the levels "Normal" for continuous data, "Poisson" for categorical data and "Binomial" for binary data. The binomial distribution generates binary data, because the number of trials is set to 1 in the implementation. The correlation between input variables is a factor with the levels 0, 0.5 and 0.8.

4.2 Fitting models and calculating accuracy

The original plan for this step was to use the unmodified code provided by the authors. In this setup, for each of the 252 different configurations of input parameters, 150 logistic regression models are fitted on a response, that is randomly generated for each of the models. Based on the classification performed by these models, the model accuracy is calculated for each set of input parameters.

This approach was not successful, since the run time for each line of input we tried out was more than an hour, even for the simplest configurations with 10 input variables and a sample size of 500. Our first strategy to cut down the run time was to simply reduce the number of input lines passed to the simulation. However, we quickly realised that this would leave us with insufficient input for the further steps of the experiment and moreover, it still took a long time to run. The next approach was to reduce the number of models that are fitted for each configuration of input parameters, which would, hopefully allow us to get at least a couple of data points for each setting. We decided to fit six models per input combination. Unfortunately, even with this drastic reduction, we were not able to get results for the combinations with more than ten input variables due to a lack of computational power. However, we still managed every setting for all the remaining parameters. To generate a sufficient amount of data in a reasonable time period, we split up the input configurations among the three members of our group and ran it on separate machines. For this we needed to modify the code with the following lines to get CSV files instead of one big Rdata file.

Listing 1: Modified code

```
colnames(resultsFinal)[1:9] <- c("col", "row",
  "distribution", "corr",
  "power", "effect",
  "type", "corrT", "amount")
name <- paste(j, n, dist, p, i, ef, ".csv")
write.csv(resultsFinal, name)
```

The head of the result of such a output of one input configuration is shown in table 2. There are multiple parameters calculated which are not directly needed for the experiment setup, such as specificity or recall. The parameters can be explained as:

- Accuracy**: calculated accuracy of logistic regression model for each simulation setting
- type**: pattern used to artificially generate missing data
- row**: sample size
- col**: number of input variables
- power**: predictive power of input variables
- distribution**: distribution from which generated data is derived as factor with level 1,2,3 for Bernoulli, Gaussian, Poisson
- corrT**: correlation of input variables in the Toeplitz Matrix needed to determine the correlation for the NORTA algorithm
- corr**: correlation between input variables
- effect**: effect size
- Specificity**: model specificity
- Precision**: model precision

Table 2: First 6 output rows as an example

	col	row	distribution	corr	power	effect	type	corrT	amount	Accuracy	Specificity	Precision	Recall	F1
res	10	500	1	0	0.2	12.96	COM	1	1	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.91	0.88
res	10	500	1	0	0.2	12.96	MCAR	0.5	0.9	0.84	0.78	0.81	0.89	0.85
res	10	500	1	0	0.2	12.96	MCAR	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.86	0.90	0.89	0.91

amount: Proportion of complete observations

For further analysis we only need to consider row, col, distribution, power, effect, type, amount and accuracy. For row, col, distribution, power and effect, the settings are identical to the settings described for n, j, dist, pref in table 1. type refers to the pattern that was used for artificially removing data from the data sets generated in the first step. The four patterns are MCAR ("Missing Completely at Random"), MNAR ("Missing Not at Random"), MAR ("Missing at Random") and COM("Complete Data"), which are further explained in the original paper. The accuracy is not fixed this time, but rather the calculated model accuracy for each simulation setting.

4.3 Quantifying the effects of each parameter

According to the authors, a simple yet effective way of achieving this is to fit a linear regression model with Accuracy as the response and col, row, distribution, corr, power, effect, type and amount. The model is fit without interaction effects in the paper, since only the main effects explained roughly 70% of the variability of the data, which the authors considered sufficient. The coefficients of the regression model can then be used as indicators of the impact of each input variable. We were able to replicate this step without

further problems and received a table of regression coefficients as a result, which we can interpret and compare to the corresponding table provided in the original paper.

As we had no data for 50 and 200 variables because we could not fit the models for these data sets, what we already described in 4.2, we could not calculate any coefficients for these variables of the linear model. The coefficients in the paper are given in percentage values so our estimates are multiplied by 100 to get a better comparison. Furthermore we will only compare the order of magnitude and the sign as a more detailed comparison would not be reasonable because of the big discrepancies between the data sets on which the model was fit.

We can see in table 3 that our estimated intercept is larger than the one estimated in the paper which can be explained by the missing configurations with 50 and 200 input variables, which lower the overall accuracy. Because we do not have those configurations we do not have any estimates for NINPUT_50 and NINPUT_200. An explanation for the difference in magnitude between the estimates in the paper and our estimates for SS_1000 and SS_10000 is that the impact of increasing the sample size is far greater for models with more input variables, which again, we do not have. The correlation estimates CINPUT_0.5 and CINPUT_0.8 are in a similar order of magnitude and the sign is the same for correlation of 0.8. The

Figure 1: Regression coefficients plus/minus three standard errors

Table 3: Comparison of regression coefficients

Parameter	Estimate Paper	Our estimate
Intercept	79.61	85.55
NINPUT_50	-4.52	NA
NINPUT_200	-19.53	NA
SS_1000	6.31	0.69
SS_10000	14.89	0.97
CINPUT_0.5	-0.08	0.07
CINPUT_0.8	-0.23	-0.15
TINPUT_Poisson	4.06	3.45
TINPUT_Gauss	8.50	5.90
PPINPUT_0.5	-0.07	0.053
PPINPUT_0.8	0.36	-0.037
TMD_MCAR	-1.46	-0.49
TMD_MAR	-4.07	-39.38
TMD_MNAR	-4.67	0.43
PMD_0.9	2.27	0.26

distribution coefficients are in the same order of magnitude. The PPIINPUT_0.5 and PPIINPUT_0.8 do neither fit the order of magnitude nor the sign is right. The coefficients on the type of pattern to artificially remove data points are in about the same order of magnitude with the difference being within the range of factor 10. The same can be said about PMD_0.9.

To compare the coefficients one could theoretically run two sample t-tests, however, this was not possible in our case as the data set we used to fit our regression model differs significantly from the one the authors may have used. Moreover we did not have access to the exact data set used in the paper, which kept us from

calculating its sample variance, which is required for the test. So we decided on comparing the regression coefficients using error bar plots that display the estimates plus an error of three standard deviations.

Most of the coefficients are significantly different as shown in 1, as the ranges of plus/minus three standard deviations of each point estimator of the coefficients are not overlapping. The only three coefficients which are not obviously significantly different are CINPUT_0.5, CINPUT_0.8 and PPIINPUT_0.5 as the intervals are overlapping. These differences are most likely due to the different data set on which we fit the linear model. The code for the generation of the data set can be found on Zenodo³.

4.4 Replication of plots

To summarise their findings, the authors included an error bar plot containing the interval from the first to the third quantile of the accuracy for each combination of simulation settings. Since we had to exclude the simulation settings with 100 and 500 input variables due to a lack of computational power, we could only replicate the part of the plot that corresponds to the configurations with 10 input variables, which is exactly the first row of the original plot. To recreate the plot we used a combination of functions from the ggplot2 library in R, including the geom_errorbar() function and facet_grid() to create the necessary plot grid.

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5913142>

Figure 3: Reproduced plot

5 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

First we summarise the results from the paper and then compare them to our findings. Before we proceed, we would like to emphasize once more that all the results we produced were derived from a data set that did not include the full range of simulation configuration that was presented in the paper. Results may vary if all the input configurations are taken into consideration.

5.1 Findings of the original paper

We begin by summarising the main results of the original paper. According to the authors, the impact of missing data decreases as the sample size increases and grows as the number of input variables increases. Binary data is affected the worst by missing data, the accuracy increases from Bernoulli to Poisson and from Poisson to Gaussian. The estimation of the accuracy gets more precise with a larger sample size, which can be seen in the length of the interquartile range, which gets narrower as the sample size grows. Moreover, they claim that the MNAR pattern for missing values affects the accuracy the worst. The correlation between the input variables as well as the missing patterns have low influence at all [2].

5.2 Findings we could confirm

Similar to the authors, we get the result, that model accuracy is the lowest for binary input data and the highest for Gaussian inputs, which can clearly be seen in fig. 3. This is also reflected by the corresponding regression coefficients. The base level for comparison is the Bernoulli distribution which is contained in the intercept. `TINPUT_Poisson` has a coefficient of 3.45 and `TINPUT_Gauss` a coefficient of 5.90, which means that the expected accuracy increases by 3.45%, for Poisson distribution and 5.9% for normal distribution compared to binary input variables.

We could also confirm that the precision of the accuracy seems to increase with the sample size. In fig. 3 it is clearly visible that the interquartile range becomes narrower as the sample size grows. This is equally the case for each of the types of distributions for the input.

We also found that the correlation level of the input variables has little impact on the expected accuracy. The regression coefficients for `CINPUT_0.5` and `CINPUT_0.8` are 0.07 and -0.15 respectively. That means that compared to a scenario, where all the input variables are uncorrelated, a correlation of 0.5 increases the expected accuracy by 0.07% and a correlation of 0.8 decreases the expected accuracy by 0.15%.

5.3 Discrepancies

As already mentioned we could not take the impact of the number of input variables into consideration. The difference in the coefficient for the missing pattern MAR compared to the other is far greater in the replication of the paper than the original one. Furthermore, the effect of the increase in sample size is far lower than for the original paper. This may be due to the lack of negative impact of the higher number variables on the accuracy.

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